

Gurez Sheep: Threatened breed of Gurez valley of Kashmir

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Gurez is a well-known breed of sheep limited to only Gurez Tehsil located in the basin of the River Kishan Ganga in District Bandipora of Kashmir Division of Jammu and Kashmir and is popular for its meat and fiber suitable for making apparel or carpet. In addition to these, it also provides a little amount of milk. The breed is well adapted to the local agro-climatic and geophysical conditions of Gurez valley. This breed plays an important role in the livelihood of the weaker sections, mainly the 'Dardi' tribe of the society. Most of this breed has now been crossed with Merino in order to increase the fibers suitable for making apparel or carpet wool due to which the population of this breed is considered declining. Gurez sheep is small to medium in size, generally white in color, although some animals are brown or black or spotted. The majority of the animals were found polled, but Poly-ceros conditions are also reported. Gurez sheep is a seasonal breeder and exhibits estrus during spring and autumn only. The breeding season ranges from April to May and August to December. Spring was a major lambing season and ewes mostly exhibited estrus during late summer and early autumn.

Introduction

The pastoral areas of state are found both in the sub-tropical zone of Jammu and the temperate zone of Kashmir. Sheep and goat rearing are the core activity of rural masses in the state and play a vital role in the socio-economic upliftment of weaker sections of the society. Sheep rearing is not a new enterprise for Jammu and Kashmir but practiced from times immemorial. Jammu and Kashmir are home to many sheep breeds including Gurez sheep. Gurez breed of sheep is the 4th registered breed of Ovine germplasm of India, with its breeding tract in Bandipora district of Jammu and Kashmir. The breed is limited to only Gurez valley and is popular for its meat and fiber suitable for making apparel or carpet. In addition to these, it also provides a little amount of milk. The breed is well adapted to the local agro-climatic and geophysical conditions of Gurez valley. The breed is known for sturdiness, adaptability, disease resistance, and mutton production. Gurez sheep are small to medium in size with white, brown, black, and their varying shades. The overall population of Gurez breed in different regions of

Gurez and Tulial valley is around 51921 out of which only 12% are pure local breed by phenotypically.

Distribution and breeding tract

Gurez is a well-known breed of sheep limited to only Gurez Tehsil located in the basin of the River Kishan Ganga in District Bandipora of Kashmir Division of Jammu and Kashmir. The breeding tract Gurez sheep is located between longitude 74°40' to 74°90' East and latitude 34°15' to 34°45' North with a minimum elevation of about 3200 M above mean sea level (AMSL) and the maximum height of the inhabited village is 4100 m.

Socio-economic status of the Sheep farmers

Family size: The family size of farmers rearing Gurez sheep ranges from 4 to 14 members

Category of the farmers: Only Marginal farmers were observed responsible for rearing for Gurez sheep.

Family type: Joint family: 35.71 %, nuclear family: 64.29 %

Education: The highest population engaged with sheep rearing was illiterate: 50.00 %, Middle standard: 28.57 %. Primary: 7.14% and post-metric: 14.29.

Community: Muslims

Tribe: Dardi tribe.

Landholding: The overall landholding per household: 7.27 Kanals, irrigated/ family: 0.49 and un-irrigated land holdings/ family: 6.78 Kanals,

Marital Status: Married.

Gender: Male:100 %.

Age: 67.86 % belonged to the middle age group between 40-59 years followed by the young aged group 20-39 (21.43 %) and the old-aged group >60 (10.71).

Occupation: 75.00% had crops+livestock as their major occupation followed by 21.43% who had livestock and labor as the main occupation and 3.57 had livestock + Government job as the main occupation.

Interaction with farmers

Physical traits of Gurez Sheep

Color: The coat color is predominantly white in both sexes few animals are brown and black.

Horns: Normally, two horns are present, but sometimes polycerrous with the maximum number of horns to be six. The horns were brown to creamy and curved

Ears: The ears are horizontal, long, thin, and pointed with varying length

Wattles: Present in less than 5% of the population

Head: Broad and long face with a convex nasal bridge.

Tail: Straight, thick at the base, and short to medium in length.

Udder pattern: The females have medium-sized udder with small conical teats.

Coat pattern: Woolly coat with short fleece length at six months and medium at 12 months age.

Special Feature: **Multiple** horns with 4 to 6.

Male

Female

Morphometric traits

Body weight (kgs): Adult Male: 30-37, Adult Female: 39-42

Body Length (cms): Adult Male: 67-74, Adult Female: 68-75

Chest Girth (cms): Adult Male: 77-86, Adult Female: 80-88

Height at withers (cms): Adult Male: 59-67, Adult Female: 59-67

Ear Length (cms): Adult Male: 6.1-10.9, Adult Female: 6.2-11.0

Tail Length (cms): Adult Male: 15.09-25, Adult Female: 14.20-22

Reproduction traits

Age at first mating (months): Male: 15-24, Female: 18-24

Age at first estrus (months): 20-30

Estrus cycle duration (days): 20-24

Estrus duration (hours): 24-36

Age at first lambing (months): 25-32

Lambing interval (months): 12-14

Litter size: 1.5

Lifetime number of lambs: 7-8

Production traits

Wool traits

Clean wool yield (%): Male: 77.47, Female: 76.68

Fiber diameter (μ): Male: 30.37, Female: 29.28

Staple length (cms): Male: 4.85, Female: 4.74

Number of crimps per centimeter: Male: 5.10, Female: 4.98

Medullation % age: Male: 9.45, Female: 9.07

Carcass traits

Age at slaughter (months): Male: 20-24, Female: 64

Weight at slaughter (kgs): Male 36, Female: 43

Carcass weight (kgs): Male: 21, Female: 23

Dressing percentage: Male: 57, Female: 55

Milk traits

Milk production on 7th day (gms): 75-300

Milk production on 50th day (gms): 300-550

Average Lifetime production (months): 97.50

Diseases and their management

Easily preventable diseases Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) pneumonia, foot rot, and ectoparasites among sheep were prevalent resulting in loss of performance, increased morbidities, and mortalities. Vaccination and dosing were seldom carried out by the Animal and Sheep Husbandry Departments. Sheep rearers were unaware of dipping and provision of salt licks. Provision of timely health cover *viz.* dosing, vaccination, dipping, and supplementation can mitigate most of the health problems observed in the area.